

Effect of Partial Reduction on Electrical and Photoelectrochemical Properties of Ferric Oxide

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Reduction of ferric oxide in a mixture of H_2 - H_2O vapour, increases the conductivity due to doping by Fe^{II} . Re-oxidation of the reduced Fe_2O_3 leads to gradual decrease of conductivity, upto a level much higher than that of the original material. The presence of Fe^{II} introduces a donor level near to the conduction band of iron oxide resulting in a decrease in the activation energy of conduction from 1.08 eV for stoichiometric ferric oxide to 0.48 eV for the re-oxidised sample.

While the re-oxidised material exhibited anodic photoconductivity towards oxygen evolution, neither the original Fe_2O_3 , nor the reduced samples are photoactive. The latter supports appreciable anodic and cathodic currents in the dark.

Solar energy conversion through the use of ferric oxide semiconductors, as photoanodes¹ or photocathodes² in a photoelectrochemical cell (PEC), has been extensively investigated. x - Fe_2O_3 was used as an electrode in the form of single crystals³, polycrystalline compressed discs¹ or thin films^{4,5}. Ferric oxide has special interest because of its moderate band-gap⁶ (2.2 eV) and high stability in aqueous solutions in a wide pH range^{6,7}. Attempts have been made to improve the photoelectrochemical properties of iron oxide by doping with different foreign impurities, e.g. Ti, Mg and Zr. The photoelectrochemical properties of ferric oxide, in terms of its photocurrent and photocatalytic activity, were improved markedly upon its partial reduction⁸. The reduced species, Fe^{II} was found to resist oxidation since it exists under a protective layer of ferric oxide⁹. The electrochemical and the semiconducting properties of ferric oxide have been reviewed¹⁰.

In the present work, we report the effect of Fe^{II} , generated by H_2 -reduction and adjusted by O_2 -oxidation, on the electrical and photoelectrochemical properties of ferric oxide.

Results and Discussion

Stability of reduced ferric oxide: The Fe_2O_3 pellets were subjected to reduction in an atmosphere of H_2 - H_2O vapour mixture for 1 h at 400°. They were subsequently re-oxidised in air, for a constant period of 1 h at various re-oxidation temperatures. In each case, the sample was cooled in air down to the room temperature before measuring the electrical conductivity (σ). The room temperature conductivity is a significant property of the material since photoelectrochemical measurements are performed at room temperature. Table 1 lists the conductivity of the reduced materials after re-oxidation at different temperatures. The conductivity of the reduced sample is about seven orders of magnitudes greater than that of the stoichiometric material. Such an increase in the conductivity is

due to the formation of Fe^{II} which is considered as anion dopant. The formation of Fe^{II} was detected by X-ray diffraction analysis which showed the peak of the (220) spinel reflection of Fe_3O_4 (Fig. not shown). The latter was formed upon reduction of Fe_2O_3 , according to

The increase in the conductivity is thus due to the increase in the carrier concentration (Fe^{II}). Both the quantities are related by the equation,

$$\sigma = en\mu_n \quad (2)$$

where e is the electronic charge, μ_n the n -carrier mobility and n the carrier concentration which is proportional to the concentration of Fe^{II} .

TABLE 1—ROOM TEMPERATURE CONDUCTIVITY OF RE-OXIDISED IRON OXIDE*

Re-oxidation temp. (°C)	Conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 25°
25	1.04×10^{-4}
100	9.76×10^{-5}
150	8.33×10^{-5}
200	7.37×10^{-5}
300	1.6×10^{-7}
400	7.6×10^{-8}
450	2.8×10^{-8}
500	1.4×10^{-9}
Stoichiometric Fe_2O_3	1.4×10^{-11}

*In each case the sample was reduced for 1 h at 400°; re-oxidation time is 1 h.

The result also shows that the room temperature conductivity decreases as the re-oxidation temperature increases. This decrease in the conductivity is due to re-oxidising Fe^{II} to Fe^{III} ,

The re-oxidation of the Fe_3O_4 was detected by X-ray diffraction analysis; the intensity of the (220) spinel reflection peak decreases as the re-oxidation temperature increases.

Activation energy of conduction: The reduced samples were re-oxidised in air at 400° for 1 h. The conductivity of this re-oxidised pellet was measured at various temperatures (25–250°). The conductivities measured upon increasing and decreasing of the temperature, are indifferent, indicating that the stoichiometry of the material did not change during the course of conductivity measurement. Plots of $\ln \sigma$ against $1/T$ for both stoichiometric and re-oxidised samples are linear in accordance with the Arrhenius equation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-q/kT) \quad (4)$$

The activation energies were found to be 1.04 and 0.48 eV for the stoichiometric and the reduced materials, respectively. The value of 1.04 eV for the activation energy of conduction in ferric oxide is in good agreement with the reported value¹¹. The activation energy of the stoichiometric material is equivalent to half of its band-gap E_g , which is⁶ 2.2 eV. On the other hand, the activation energy of the re-oxidised sample is equivalent to the donor ionisation energy¹² E_d . E_d is related to E_g by

$$E_d = E_g - E_1 \quad (5)$$

where E_1 is the ground state energy of the donor (Fe^{II}). According to equation (5), $E_1 = 1.60$ eV; thus the relatively low value of the activation energy of conduction, in the case of the re-oxidised material, is attributed to the fact that the ground state energy of the donor (Fe^{II}) is 1.60 eV higher than the corresponding energy level in the stoichiometric material.

Electrochemical and photoelectrochemical measurements: Since the conductivity of the stoichiometric ferric oxide, $10^{-11} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, is too low, its i - E relation could not be taken. On the other hand, the conductivity of the reduced sample was relatively high (Table 1). The i - E curves for the reduced sample in 0.1 N NaOH and also in 0.1 N H_2SO_4 are shown in Figs. 1a and 1b, respectively. In Fig. 1a, the cathodic current starts to increase exponentially at -1.05 V vs SCE. This negative current is due to the H_2 evolution reaction which is expected to commence at a potential more negative than -1.0 V vs SCE. On the other hand, the positive current starting at -0.3 V vs SCE is due to O_2 evolution which is expected at a potential more positive than 0.20 V vs SCE. In 0.1 N H_2SO_4 the H^+ reduction and O_2 evolution occur below -0.25 and above $+1.25$ V vs SCE, respectively (Fig. 1b). Upon illuminating the reduced ferric oxide sample, significant photocurrents could not be recorded (neither in NaOH nor in H_2SO_4) revealing that the process of the electron-hole separation is not efficient enough in the highly conductive reduced material.

For an iron oxide sample, reduced in H_2 - H_2O and then re-oxidised in air, the i - E curves, in the dark and upon illumination, are shown in Fig. 2. The cathodic dark current increases exponentially with the negative potential. This current is limited,

Fig. 1. i - E curves of the reduced iron oxide anode obtained by scanning from left to right at 0.2 V min^{-1} . The electrolyte was: (a) 0.1 N NaOH and (b) 0.1 N H_2SO_4 .

indicating that the re-oxidised sample is less active than the reduced one in catalysing the O_2 evolution reaction. Upon illuminating the re-oxidised sample it shows no change in the cathodic current (Fig. 2)

and a significant increase in the anodic current. This anodic photoactivity increases with the magnitude of applied positive bias. The anodic photocurrent on the semiconducting material is equivalent to the hydrogen evolution current on the platinum counter electrode.

The i - E relation (Fig. 2) is a typical characteristic of an n-type material. In such a material, the cathodic dark current increases with the negative bias because it is due to the injection of electrons, which are the majority carriers, into the solution. On the other hand, the injection of holes into the solution causes the anodic current. This anodic dark current is limited because the holes are minority carriers. The photogeneration of holes, upon illumination, causes the anodic photocurrent to increase. The fact that the re-oxidised sample is an active photoanode, while the reduced sample is not, indicates that the process of the electron-hole separation in the former is more efficient than in the latter.

Fig. 2 Current-voltage scan obtained with a pellet of the re-oxidised iron oxide anode by scanning from left to right at 0.2 V min^{-1} : (—) in dark and (---) under illumination by 20 mW cm^{-2} of visible light; 0.1 N NaOH solution was used as an electrolyte.

Experimental

Ferric oxide powder (Alfa products; 99.991%) was compressed into pellets under 10^4 kg cm^{-2} , and sintered in air at 1000° for 24 h. The sintered pellets were reduced in a stream of 95% H_2 -5% H_2O vapour mixture at 300 – 400° . They were re-oxidised in air at 300 – 500° .

Electrical conductivity: Both faces of the pellets were polished with alumina powder ($1 \mu\text{m}$) and cleaned with a 1 : 1 acetone-methanol mixture. The pellets were coated with silver paint and mounted between two Ag electrodes. The conductivity

measurements were made by the current-voltage technique. The temperature of the samples was controlled by an alumel-chromel thermocouple in an electrical furnace.

Electrochemical measurements: For electrochemical measurements, the iron oxide electrode was prepared by spreading a thin layer of indium-gallium eutectic over one side of the pellet. A copper wire was connected to the same side of the pellet by using Ag epoxy (Tra-Con, Bipex). The wire and the epoxy were then coated with silicon rubber (Dow Corning, Silastic 732 RTV). Electrochemical measurements were carried out in a three-compartment pyrex cell. An iron oxide pellet served as the working electrode, a Pt foil (1 cm^2 area) as the counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. Measurements were performed either in 0.1 N NaOH or $0.1 \text{ N H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Current-voltage curves, in the dark and upon illumination, were obtained on an X-Y recorder by using a cyclic potentiostat. Illumination of the working electrode was made by a 250 W halogen-tungsten lamp. The light was filtered from infrared by passing through a water jacket, and from uv by a 420 nm cut-off filter. The intensity of the light beam was 15 – 20 mW cm^{-2} as measured by a calibrated Epply thermopile.

X-Ray diffraction: Powder of ferric oxide, treated like the pellets, was subjected to X-ray diffraction using a Siemens D 500 diffractometer equipped with a copper K_α radiation source. Measurements were undertaken in the range from $2\theta = 15^\circ$ to 65° .

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